

Spectroscopic Evidence for the Generation of Singlet Oxygen Dimers

C. I. ANUNUSO

Department of Chemistry, School of Science, Federal University of Technology, P. N. B. 1526, Owerri, Nigeria

Manuscript received 13 December 1987, revised 29 June 1990, accepted 22 August 1990

Singlet oxygen dimers $2[{}^1\Delta]$ and $2[{}^1\Sigma]$ have been observed at 350, 630 and 725 nm on decomposition of organic peroxides. The intensity of emission decreases in the order, 2-methyl butanoyl peroxide > phenyl acetyl peroxide > hexanoyl peroxide, reflecting the structural features required for the decomposition of *p*- and sec-alkyl-peroxyl radicals by the Russell's scheme.

THERMALLY-induced homolytic decomposition of diacyl peroxides has been used extensively as a source of alkyl and acyl radicals^{1,2} (equations 1 and 2). The reaction of alkyl radicals with dissolved oxygen (equation 3) gives peroxyl radicals which, if they have an α -hydrogen, may undergo a self-reaction via the Russell³ Scheme (equation 4).

The recombination of two peroxyl radicals, yields energies⁴ of about 115–150 kcal mol⁻¹. For luminescent excitation of carbonyl triplets, energies in the range of 75–80 kcal mol⁻¹ are required⁵. The production of carbonyl triplets with efficiencies of the order of unity was observed by Kellogg⁶.

The object of the present work is to study the effect on chemiluminescence by varying the structure of the alkyl radicals used in the autoxidation.

Results and Discussion

Four diacyl peroxides were prepared, viz. hexanoyl, 2-methylbutanoyl, pivaloyl and phenyl-

acetyl peroxides. The chemiluminescence emission on decomposition at $52 \pm 2^\circ$ was measured in two solvents. The relative light yields in benzene and toluene are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—RELATIVE LIGHT YIELDS (ARBITRARY UNITS)

Peroxide	Benzene	Toluene
Hexanoyl	3.2×10^5	3.3×10^5
2-Methylbutanoyl	1.7×10^5	1.3×10^5
Pivaloyl	4.5×10^5	8.0×10^5
Phenylacetyl	7.9×10^5	2.1×10^6

When oxygen was bubbled through these solvents an increased emission was observed (Table 2) (*cf.* light yield in benzene and toluene respectively before and after oxygen bubbling through these solvents).

TABLE 2—RELATIVE LIGHT YIELDS (ARBITRARY UNITS)

Peroxide	Benzene	Toluene
Hexanoyl	4.0×10^5	5.1×10^5
2-Methylbutanoyl	4.2×10^5	2.6×10^5
Pivaloyl	4.1×10^5	8.8×10^5
Phenylacetyl	13.5×10^5	4.2×10^6

The rate constants (*K*) for the decomposition of diacyl peroxides in toluene at $44 \pm 1^\circ$ are as follows: hexanoyl, 122.4×10^{-4} ; 2-methylbutanoyl, 9.88×10^{-4} ; pivaloyl, 42.7×10^{-4} ; phenylacetyl, 51.7×10^{-4} .

Diacyl peroxides (RCOO)₂ decompose thermally by oxygen-oxygen bond homolysis at similar rates as revealed by the values of *K*. The kinetics are complicated by cage recombination of the primary fragments if R = phenyl or primary alkyl⁶. In contrast, peroxides in which R is a secondary or tertiary alkyl or a resonance-stabilised fragment, the decomposition is probably a concerted process involving breakage of two or more bonds⁷ (equations 1, 2).

The rate constants⁸ for bimolecular self-reaction carbon-centred radicals including resonance-stabi-

lised radicals are approximately $2 \times 10^9 M^{-1}$. This implies that the chain termination rate constant for reaction (5) will be approximately similar when R=primary, secondary or tertiary.

The alkyl radicals formed in reaction (2) are transformed into alkyl peroxy radicals (3) by a diffusion-controlled reaction with oxygen. The rate constant³ for this reaction is between 10^{10} and $10^{11} M^{-1} s^{-1}$.

The generally accepted mechanism for the self-reaction of primary and secondary peroxy radicals is due to Russell³. Bartlett and Guaraldi⁹ obtained evidence for the existence of peroxy radical-tetroxide equilibrium at temperatures $< 100^\circ$ in autoxidation.

The decrease (Fig. 1, Table 1) in chemiluminescence following thermal decomposition and autoxidation in benzene of 2-methylbutanoyl peroxide, phenylacetyl peroxide and hexanoyl peroxide reflects the structural features required for decomposition of I (equation 4).

Fig. 1. Chemiluminescence from diacyl peroxide in benzene at $52 \pm 2^\circ$.

Rate constants for chain termination ($2k_t$) in autoxidation of hydrocarbons giving non-tertiary peroxy radicals are generally faster than for hydrocarbons giving tertiary peroxy radicals¹⁰. For primary peroxy radicals $RCH_2OO\cdot$, $2k_t$ values are $2-4 \times 10^8 M^{-1} s^{-1}$, and for sec-peroxy radicals, $2k_t$ is from 2×10^6 to $4 \times 10^7 M^{-1} s^{-1}$ range^{8,11}.

In Russell's mechanism, reaction proceeds by rapid α -hydrogen transfer via a cyclic transition state I available to tetroxides of *p*- and sec-alkyl radicals but not to t-alkyl tetroxides¹².

Differences in chemiluminescent yields have shown that termination rate constants are highly dependent on the structure of the peroxy radical. The α -hydrogen will be more firmly bound in a peroxy radical derived from a saturated hydrocarbon than in one in which the peroxy group is adjacent to a π -electron system. Howard and Ingold¹² confirmed Russell's conclusion that the

rate constant for termination of sec-alkylperoxy radicals depends on the strength of the C-H bond.

A mechanism involving the intermediacy of alkoxy radicals is similar to that described by reactions (6-9). Hiatt and Zigmund¹³ showed that the interaction of two sec-butylperoxy radicals does not give di-sec-butyl peroxide at 318 K, a product that might be expected if the reaction involves the intermediacy of sec-butoxy radicals. The chemiluminescence which accompanies decomposition of pivaloyl peroxide in benzene cannot proceed via the Russell³ mechanism because of the absence of the structural features required for the reaction (Fig. 1). Blanchard¹⁴ proposed a non-chain terminating mechanism for tertiary peroxy radicals (equations 6-9). This reaction also proceeds via a tetroxide intermediate^{9,15,16,17} (equation 6).

The chain termination rate constants of t-alkylperoxy radicals are generally lower (1×10^{-8} to $5 \times 10^4 M^{-1} s^{-1}$) than those of sec-alkylperoxy and *p*-alkylperoxy radicals^{10,11}. The main products of this slow reaction are t-alkoxy radicals and oxygen.

In toluene (SH), the reaction is complicated by steps (10-12) which in the presence of oxygen generates primary benzylperoxy radicals ($SOO\cdot$).

These solvent-derived peroxy radicals undergo autoxidations similar to those previously described using benzene as solvent.

The solvent effect is shown by the increased chemiluminescent yield from hexanoyl (primary) and pivaloyl (tertiary) peroxides but a decrease in yield for 2-methylbutanoyl (sec) peroxide (Figs. 2 and 3, Table 1). When oxygen was bubbled through the decomposition solvents, the increased chemiluminescence underlines the stoichiometric nature of reaction (3) (Table 2). The light yield for 2-methylbutanoyl peroxide in benzene as solvent (Tables 1 and 2) is 1.7×10^5 , increasing to 4.2×10^5 when oxygen was bubbled through the solvent. Similarly an increase of 1.3×10^5 to 2.6×10^5 was recorded for this peroxide in toluene as solvent when oxygen was bubbled through the solvent.

Fig 2. Chemiluminescence from diacyl peroxide in toluene at $52 \pm 1^\circ$.

Fig 3. Chemiluminescence from diacyl peroxide in toluene at $52 \pm 2^\circ$.

2-Methylbutanoyl peroxide is a secondary peroxide. The solvent-derived peroxide when the decomposition solvent is toluene is expected to be a primary peroxide. The difference in structure of the solvent derived peroxide affects the termination rate constant because the α -hydrogen will be more bound in a primary peroxy radical as against one in which the peroxy group is adjacent to an electron-rich center^{1,2}. This explains the decrease in chemiluminescence yield observed for 2-methylbutanoyl peroxide in going from benzene to toluene as solvents.

Conservation of spin multiplicity rule suggests that there are two possible products from the decomposition of the cyclic transition state I (equation 4). In the first mode of decomposition, excited carbonyl compound would be formed in the triplet state while oxygen would be eliminated in the triplet ground state. In the second mode of

decomposition, molecular oxygen would be produced in an excited singlet state ($^1\Sigma$ or $^1\Delta$) while the carbonyl compound is in the singlet ground state.

The recorded chemiluminescence (CL) spectra in benzene (Figs. 4–6) have shown that the emission lies in the red at about 630 nm and 725 nm with a contribution at 350 nm. It seems reasonable to assign the CL emission to the transitions $2(^1\Sigma) \rightarrow 2(^3\Sigma)$ at ~ 350 nm and $2(^1\Delta) \rightarrow 2(^3\Sigma)$ at 630 and 725 nm. The decomposition of pivaloyl peroxide in benzene as solvent produced a weak spectrum.

Nakano *et al.*¹⁸ provided spectroscopic evidence for the production of both $^1\Sigma^+$ and $^1\Delta$ states of singlet oxygen in aqueous oxidation of sec-butyl

Fig 4. Chemiluminescence spectrum from phenylacetyl peroxide in benzene at $52 + 2^\circ$.

Fig 5. Chemiluminescence spectrum from hexanoyl peroxide in benzene at $52 + 2^\circ$.

Fig. 6. Chemiluminescence spectrum from 2-methylbutanoyl peroxide in benzene at $52 \pm 2^\circ$.

hydroperoxide or linoleic acid hydroperoxide by ceric ion. In the disproportionation reaction of *sec*-peroxyl radicals, Kellogg⁵ concluded that the major product is carbonyl triplets. Singlet oxygen present is produced directly from reaction (4) or by ground triplet state oxygen quenching of the excited carbonyl compound. It is difficult to ascertain whether excited carbonyl triplets are produced initially by the decomposition of the cyclic transition state (equation 4). The CL emission at 630 and 725 nm cannot be due to an excited carbonyl triplet. Kellogg's⁵ conclusion that excited carbonyls are produced with an efficiency of the order of unity is based on the rate constants for triplet ground state oxygen quenching of chemiluminescence. It is estimated that only one excited carbonyl triplet in 10^8 emits due to competition with quenching in the solvent cage (equation 4).

The recorded chemiluminescence spectrum shows certain similarities to emission from singlet oxygen $2[{}^1\Delta]$, $2[{}^1\Sigma]$ dimers as reported earlier^{18,19}. The decomposition of the Russell⁹ cyclic intermediate (equation 4) may have generated triplet carbonyl with similar efficiency to that reported by Kellogg⁵. Due to the long life-time of excited triplet carbonyls, quenching interaction by triplet ground state oxygen within the solvent cage may lead to the production of singlet oxygen. Hence the observed emission may be termed oxyluminescence. Earlier workers¹⁸ have reported spectroscopic evidence for the generation of singlet oxygen (${}^1\Sigma$, ${}^1\Delta$) and (${}^1\Delta$, ${}^1\Delta$) dimers.

Experimental

Hexanoic acid, 2-methylbutyric acid and pivalic acid (all Aldrich), phenylacetic acid and thionyl

chloride (both B.D.H.) were used. Thionyl chloride was purified before use by fractionation from quinoline, the distillate then refractionated from boiled linseed oil and fraction with b.p. $76-78^\circ$ was collected. Toluene and benzene (both B.D.H.) were dried with sodium.

Diacyl peroxides were prepared²⁰ by treating the respective acyl chlorides with potassium superoxide (KO_2) and stored in dichloromethane below 0° : hexanoyl peroxide, 65% (yield); 2-methylbutanoyl peroxide, 65%; phenylacetyl peroxide, 63%; pivaloyl peroxide, 69%. The rate of peroxide decomposition in toluene (*ca.* $1 \times 10^{-5} M$) was measured iodometrically at $44 \pm 1^\circ$.

Chemiluminescence measurement was carried out in a lyoluminescence reader by adding to the decomposition solvent at $52 \pm 2^\circ$ a known concentration (*ca.* $1 \times 10^{-5} M$) of the peroxide under test. The chemiluminescence spectrum was recorded in a transient spectrophotometer.

Acknowledgement

The author is indebted to Professors K.V. Ettinger and A. R. Forrester of Department of Biomedical Physics and Bioengineering and Chemistry Department respectively of the University of Aberdeen.

A supporting grant from the International Atomic Energy Agency is gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. A. G. DAVIES, "Organic Peroxides", Butterworth, London, 1961.
2. W. A. PRYOR, "Free Radicals", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1966.
3. G. A. RUSSELL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 3871.
4. J. HINE, "Physical Organic Chemistry", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1956, p. 34.
5. R. E. KELLOGG, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **91**, 5433.
6. J. W. TAYLOR and J. C. MARTIN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **88**, 3650.
7. P. D. BARTLETT and J. E. LEFFLER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 3030.
8. "Free Radicals", ed. J. K. KOCHI, Wiley, New York, 1973, Vol. 1.
9. P. D. BARTLETT and G. J. GURALDI, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 4799.
10. J. A. HOWARD and K. U. INGOLD, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1967, **45**, 793.
11. J. A. HOWARD, *Adv. Free Radical Chem.*, 1971, **4**, 49.
12. J. A. HOWARD and K. U. INGOLD, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 1058.
13. R. HIATT and I. ZIGMUND, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1970, **48**, 3967.
14. H. S. BLANCHARD, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 4548.
15. J. E. BENNETT and J. A. HOWARD, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **95**, 4008.
16. P. O. BARTLETT and T. G. TRAYLOR, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 2407.
17. K. ADAMIC, J. A. HOWARD and K. U. INGOLD, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1969, **47**, 3803.
18. M. NAKANO, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **98**, 1972.
19. A. U. KHAN and M. KASHA, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **88**, 1574.
20. R. A. JOHNSON, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1976, 331.